

SOCIAL SUPPORT IN THE FIGHT AGAINST POVERTY

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Economic laws show that "poverty reproduces poverty." This happens for several reasons. First, poor countries cannot afford to spend enough to maintain affordable, free and high-quality health care and education, and poor people cannot afford to pay for adequate private services. As a result, the less educated and less healthy poor cannot get out of poverty due to the low quality of human potential. Secondly, the poorer the population, the lower the effective demand, the lower the capacity of the consumer market, and, accordingly, the incentives for the development of industry, agriculture, and, especially, the service sector. This, in turn, hinders the development of the economy, reduces budget revenues and, in a closed cycle, the possibilities of social support for the poor. Thirdly, the mentality of people from poor families often differs from the mentality of richer families. For the above reasons, smaller people from poor families have a creative and entrepreneurial mindset. The crime rate among people from poor families is generally higher.

In other words, poverty holds back the human development potential, the productive forces in the country and the economic activity of the population.

Over the past three years, the real total per capita income in Uzbekistan has grown by 43.9%, and the average monthly nominal accrued wages by 79.7%, or from \$126.54[1] in 2016 to \$227.34 in 2019. According to a household survey within the framework of the World Bank's Listening to the Citizens of Uzbekistan project, the average monthly income of one poor household in January-March 2020 is about 1.5 million soums or 146.70 US dollars, which is 12% more compared to the same period of last year.

President Sh. Mirziyoyev poses the problem of poverty reduction in Uzbekistan as a strategic task. Significant efforts of the government are aimed at its solution. Thus, the country has created the necessary institutions to combat poverty. This is the Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Reduction, which will determine the policy of combating poverty. To support both socially vulnerable and low-income families, the Ministry of Mahalla and Family Support was recently created. This ministry, as a responsible body for coordinating the activities of citizens' self-government bodies, should increase the efficiency of identifying socially vulnerable segments of the population.

Programs are being implemented to improve housing conditions in rural areas. In particular, thanks to the implementation of the Obod Qishloq program, the living conditions of 1.7 million villagers have been improved. A total of 6.1 trillion soums, or \$600 million in equivalent, was allocated for the implementation of the Obod Qishloq and Obod Mahalla programs in 2019.

However, despite the progress made, currently more than 400 thousand families in Uzbekistan are in need of better housing conditions, and their daily income per family member, according to official statistics, does not exceed 10-13 thousand sums (less than 1.5 US dollars). The October 2015 World Bank criteria set the global poverty rate at \$1.9 a day. The share of the informal sector in the labor market is 40-50%. However, only 23% of vulnerable households receive social benefits.

In the context of the pandemic, the need to accelerate the reform of institutions that provide social support and material assistance to the poor and the most vulnerable segments of the population has become more urgent. Therefore, these problems are being actively addressed. There is a transition from previously created insufficiently targeted and inefficient institutions for the distribution of material assistance to systemic solutions based on the digitalization of this area, providing the necessary control, transparency and targeting.

Social protection is a state policy, a set of measures and programs aimed at reducing poverty and inequality, improving the well-being of socially unprotected segments of the population. The organized social security system of the state in the Western world began to enjoy success at the beginning of the 20th century - during the creation of social security systems in Germany and Great Britain, and somewhat later in the USA - during the Great Depression. If 100 years ago social protection systems officially existed in only a few countries, today they are practically everywhere. The logic, tools and mechanisms for applying such schemes vary as countries seek to build social protection systems based on their capabilities, national circumstances and priorities.

An important role in overcoming poverty is played by the institutions of social support for the population, which are designed not only to help materially, but also to help the most vulnerable groups out of poverty. Since the 1990s, social assistance in the form of grants has been provided in developed countries with mandatory requirements to involve its recipients in legal entrepreneurship. In those countries where this practice was applied (Korea, USA, New Zealand, Great Britain, etc.), there was an active involvement of the population in employment.

The results of various studies show that a more accurate assessment of the needs of the beneficiary, based not only on the level of his income, but also taking into account other unaccounted for income, provides more effective tools in terms of combating poverty. This mechanism of complex criteria includes a comparison of declaration data with data from tax and other government agencies. These changes in the system of targeted social assistance are partly a factor in reducing the official level of poverty in countries such as Austria, Belgium, Australia, Canada, the Czech Republic, Denmark, and others in the mid-2000s.

Different countries use different schemes to reduce poverty. The Swedish model assumes the achievement of two goals: full employment and income equalization. In this Scandinavian country, they prefer to retrain the unemployed and return them to work in demanded areas.

As can be seen from the above, the problems that have accumulated over the previous years in the system of social security for the family of the population have to be solved literally in the system of manual control - obtaining information through local sectors to solve existing problems and identify those that really need government support. However, this is often a subjective solution to the issue, overly dependent on the “human factor”.

The experience of foreign countries and the identified shortcomings in the process of the study indicate that social support should be built on a systematic basis. Clear criteria for the allocation of certain types of assistance should be developed, the determination of compliance with which should be based on independent sources of information. The criteria and procedures for the distribution of aid and the specific data on the basis of which it is distributed should be transparent. In addition, it is precisely in the transition from manual management of social support issues to a clear and precise holistic system of supporting the population and reducing poverty that a lot of work has recently been done.

Important steps in this direction in the country began to be taken last year. According to the Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers dated April 15, 2019, the Unified Register of Social Protection Information System is being implemented, which conducts a transparent assessment of the degree of need of families and the compliance of applicants with the established criteria. carried out in real time. The degree of need is determined taking into account information about the income of family members, property, bank accounts, loans received, cars available in the relevant databases of various departments. Based on these

assessments, a single database of applicants and recipients of state social services and assistance is formed. To develop this system, since October 1, 2019, a pilot project has been developed in the Syrdarya region.

For the effective implementation of this system, objective data on support provided to the population must be included in the Unified Register of Social Protection. And this problem is also solved in the survey of households. Based on them and taking into account the negative impact of quarantine restrictions on the standard of living of individual families, the Ministry for Support of the Mahalla and Family and the departments responsible for the socio-economic development of the regions compiled lists in need of material assistance and support this year. The lists include the poor; citizens with disabilities; families in need of social protection; single pensioners; permanently unemployed citizens; citizens who have become unemployed due to quarantine; citizens returning from epidemiologically disadvantaged regions. These lists include more than 400 thousand families, in which there are more than 1.7 million people. To provide one-time assistance to these families, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 30, 2020 No. PP-6038 "On additional measures to materially support the population in need of assistance and social protection during the coronavirus pandemic" allocated 380 billion soums from the republican budget. Assistance was allocated in the amount of 220 thousand soums for each family member.

The next important step in this direction is the Decree of the President of August 4, 2020 "On additional measures to automate the procedures for the provision of state social services and assistance to the population." The decree establishes that from September 1 of the current year, the procedures for considering applications and assigning social payments are carried out in stages through the information system "Unified Register of Social Protection", which is an integral part of the "Electronic Government". system and will be introduced in all regions of the republic before the end of this year.

Among the main goals of introducing this system is the need to eliminate the subjective approach in decision-making through an objective assessment of the needs of low-income families according to certain criteria; a radical reduction in the number of certificates and documents required for the provision of state social services and assistance, by automating the procedures for interdepartmental electronic interaction for the exchange of documents, as well as automating the processes of providing state social services and assistance.

From January 1, 2021, the list of documents required to receive state social services and assistance is sharply limited. Certificates of recognition as low-income will be issued through the Single Portal of Interactive Public Services and are valid for twelve months. 30 billion sums have been allocated from the republican budget for the transfer of documents stored on paper in the archives of the registry office into electronic databases.

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